

IMPACT OF DIGITIZATION ON INCREASING FINANCIAL INCLUSIVITY IN THE BANKING SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Digitalization of the banking system is a key factor for the development of the financial sector and economic growth in Uzbekistan. This thesis will explore how the adoption of digital technology in the banking sector affects financial inclusion for the general population, especially in rural and remote areas. Particular attention will be paid to analyzing the current state of digitalization in Uzbek banks, identifying the main challenges and opportunities, as well as studying successful cases and best practices that can be adapted for Uzbekistan.

Currently, Uzbek banks are actively introducing digital platforms, mobile applications and online banking. These technologies significantly improve access to financial services for the population. For example, mobile applications allow you to carry out banking transactions without the need to visit branches, which is especially important for residents of remote areas. In addition, online banking provides customers with the opportunity to manage their accounts, transfer money, pay for services and carry out other financial transactions at any time and from any place where there is access to the Internet.

Among the most significant digital initiatives in the banking sector of Uzbekistan is the introduction of mobile payment systems and Internet banking. Banks offer customers the opportunity to make money transfers, pay utility bills and receive loans online. This saves time and reduces transportation costs for customers, which is especially important during the COVID-19 pandemic when physical interaction is limited. One example of successful digitalization is the “Click” project launched by the National Bank of Uzbekistan. The platform provides a wide range of services including payments, transfers and bill payments through a mobile application. Another example is the Payme system, which is also gaining popularity among the population due to its convenience and ease of use.

Diagram-1

Rating of mobile banks and applications for payments in Uzbekistan

Diagram 1 provides the ranking of mobile banks and applications for payments in Uzbekistan. This rating unites mobile banks and applications for payments - the 13 most popular services in Uzbekistan, in which residents of Uzbekistan, using a mobile phone, can make payments and transfers, track the status of financial products. The assessment reflects the quality of the digital customer experience in the application based on a comparative analysis of 13 blocks of tasks that are relevant for both types of services and are associated with transactional activity. The number of available features, their convenience and stability were taken into account.

As we can see from the diagram 1, Uzum Bank, Payme and Click payment systems are distinguished by their high convenience in solving frequency problems and wide possibilities for payments: a variety of forms of payment for utility, telecom, educational, transport services and services of budgetary organizations, both payment standards by QR code.

Despite significant progress, a number of problems remain. Firstly, access to the Internet and modern mobile devices is still limited in some regions of the country. Secondly, many citizens, especially the older generation, have difficulty using digital technologies due to low levels of digital literacy. These factors limit the potential of digitalization and require targeted solutions.

The main challenges on the path to complete digitalization of the banking sector include infrastructural and technological limitations. Insufficient high-speed internet coverage in rural areas hinders access to online services. Cybersecurity is also an important aspect, as the increase in the number of digital transactions increases the risks of fraud and cyber-attacks. Another

challenge is the regulatory environment. Effective development of digital financial services requires transparent and flexible regulations that promote innovation while protecting consumer interests and ensuring data security.

However, digitalization offers many opportunities to improve financial inclusion. Government initiatives, such as the “Digital Economy Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030,” are aimed at developing digital infrastructure and supporting innovation. Programs to improve digital literacy among the population, especially in rural and remote areas, can also significantly improve the situation.

In order to solve the above problems, the following measures are proposed:

❖ *Infrastructure improvement:*

- Expanding Internet access in rural and remote areas.
- Investing in the development of mobile networks and digital platforms.

❖ *Improving digital literacy:*

- Conducting educational programs and campaigns to improve the level of digital literacy of the population.
- Special training programs for the older generation and residents of rural areas.

❖ *Promoting Innovation:*

- Supporting startups and fintech companies through grants and investments.
- Creating a favorable regulatory environment for the introduction of new financial technologies.

❖ *Improving the regulatory environment:*

- Development of flexible and transparent regulations that stimulate digitalization.
- Ensuring data security and consumer protection.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the digitalization of the banking system of Uzbekistan represents a critical step for increasing the financial inclusion of the country. The adoption of digital technologies significantly expands access to financial services for all segments of the population, especially those living in rural and remote areas. These changes not only help improve financial inclusion, but also stimulate economic growth and improve the quality of life of the population.

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